

The Function of Apparent Diffusion Coefficient and Diffusion-Weighted Imaging in Distinguishing between Different Types of Brain Tumors

Nosiba Saeed Awad Ali^{1*}, Hussein Ahmed Hassan², Amel alsied Hasan³

¹College of Graduate Studies and Scientific Research, Karary University, Khartoum, Sudan.

²College of Medical Radiologic Science, Karary University, Khartoum, Sudan.

³Faculty of Radiological and Nuclear Medicine Science, The National Ribat University, Khartoum, Sudan.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: The second most common cause of mortality globally is tumors, and early detection is crucial for improving outcomes. Brain tumors, characterized by abnormal cell growth in the brain, can be either benign or malignant. Although conventional MRI techniques are routinely used for diagnosis, they often lack the sensitivity needed for tumor grading and characterization. By determining the apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) value for each tumor and contrasting these results with the final histology result, this study seeks to evaluate the function of Diffusion Weighted Imaging (DWI) in differentiating between common brain tumors in patients.

Methods: A retrospective analysis was conducted involving thirty-four patients who underwent MRI examinations, including conventional and DWI, at a diagnostic radiology department between January 2022 and December 2024. The study employed a 1.5-T magnetic resonance scanner, with DWI analyzed using calculated ADC values. Data on demographics, MRI characteristics, and histopathological findings were collected and analyzed using SPSS Version 27.

Results: Whole-lesion ADC center values ranged $0.470\text{--}2.854 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ higher values in dysembryoplastic neuroepithelial tumor and lower in abscess, AS for ADC border values ranged $0.770\text{--}1.672 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ higher values in pilocytic astrocytoma and lower in malignant meningioma. These results demonstrated the value of ADC in brain lesion differential diagnosis.

Conclusion: DWI and ADC are excellent supplementary imaging modalities because they are quick, simple, non-invasive, and require no contrast injection. It might be able to distinguish between various brain lesions, facilitating prompt diagnosis and care.

KEYWORDS: Apparent Diffusion Coefficient, Brain tumors, Diagnosis, Diffusion-Weighted Imaging, Imaging Techniques, MRI.

INTRODUCTION

A tumor (also called a neoplasm or lesion) is abnormal tissue that grows by uncontrolled cell division. Normal cells grow in a controlled manner as new cells replace old or damaged ones. For reasons not fully understood, tumor cells reproduce uncontrollably [1].

Unlike cancer, a tumor could be benign, pre-carcinoma, or malign. Benign tumors differ from malign in that benign generally do not spread to other organs and tissues and can be surgically removed [2].

Conventional magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) uses non-contrast T1-weighted, T2-weighted, and post-contrast T1-weighted images to diagnose brain cancers. It is believed that traditional MRI methods are insufficient for identifying, categorizing, and assessing the aggressiveness of brain tumors [3].

Conventional MRI does not provide information on the grade, aggressiveness, or histology criteria of the tumor, even though it primarily gives structural information about the tumor, including its size, location, and morphological appearance. Recent research has indicated that additional imaging modalities, like as diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI), are required for this purpose [4].

Diffusion weighted imaging (DWI) is based on the random thermic motion, or Brownian motion, of water molecules in tissues; "isotropic diffusion" is defined as unhindered diffusion of water molecules, while "anisotropic diffusion" refers to restriction of movement in some directions. The apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) of the corresponding target volume can be calculated and mapped in vivo thanks to DWI. Since the microscopic tissue architecture is reflected in ADC tumor patterns, DWI has become a crucial MRI modality, particularly in cancer imaging [6].

To reduce the risks associated with biopsy of various brain pathologies, DWI may be useful in distinguishing tumor invasion from normal brain tissue or perifocal cerebral edema [5]. Therefore, by determining the apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) value for each tumor and comparing these results with the final histology result, our study sought to evaluate the role of Diffusion Weighted Imaging (DWI) in differentiating between common brain tumors in patients.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This retrospective study was conducted from January 2022 to December 2024, involving a total of thirty-four patients. Which was conducted at the diagnostic Radiology department. The study utilized a 1.5-T magnetic resonance scanner (Toshiba), manufactured in China in January 2009. All patients included in the study underwent a comprehensive medical history review, neurological examination, histopathology result, and MRI examination (both conventional and DWI).

Conventional MRI was done in supine position using standard head coil with the head maintain in a neutral position. Sagittal and axial T1-weighted non-contrast images were done then axial T2-weighted fast spin echo image and axial fluid attenuated inversion recovery (FLAIR).

Post-contrast-enhanced axial, coronal, and sagittal T1-weighted images were obtained. Then, DWI was performing using multi-section single-shot spin echo planar imaging (EPI) sequence.

The diffusion gradients were applied sequentially in the three different kinds of images were acquired: ADC maps, trace images, and orthogonal images.

Calculation of ADC maps automatically was done by MRI software. Regions of interests (ROIs) was manually position, and all values were automatically calculated and express in $10^{-3}\text{mm}^2/\text{s}$. ADC measurements perform used a region of interest (ROI) method, with uniform ellipsoid ROI of 50–100 mm^2 area. The ROI did not involve cystic and necrotic tumor areas. The ADC calculated using (RadiAnt DICOM Viewer) software.

Four ROIs are inserted into each matching tumor. The data and statistical analysis employed mean \pm S.D. as the representative value.

A uniform enhancing zone in the middle of the tumor was covered by the first ROI. The second was placed on the edge of the tumor. The third was placed in the location of the edema if present. As for the fourth, it was placed in the area free of tumor to measure normal tissues. Four ROIs were measured (fig 1,2 and 3), and their average was calculated. The DWI + ADC value was interpreted by senior radiologist.

Fig 1 shows 45 years old male who presented with headache and dysphasia MRI shows right frontal intra-axial cystic lesion with mural nodule measuring 4.5×2.7cm with nodule measuring 1.3×1cm. the lesion surrounded by perifocal edema with effacement of cortical sulci. **A:** ADC map shows ROI on border of mural nodule area p value is $1.103 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. **B:** ADC map shows ROI on center of mural nodule p value is $1.025 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. **C:** ADC map in edema around the lesion p value is $1.51 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. **D:** ADC map shows ROI in same side normal area p value is $.7764 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. **E:** Post-contrast T1WI axial image showed marginal enhancement with enhancement of the nodule.

(Histopathology result is glioblastoma WHO grade IV)

Fig 2 shows 22 years old female who presented with headache, vertigo and vomiting MRI shows right frontal intra-axial cortical SOL measuring 1.2×1.3cm. the lesion surrounded by perifocal edema. **A:** ADC map shows ROI on center of lesion p value is $1.596 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. **B:** ADC map shows ROI on border p value is $1.345 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. **C:** ADC map in edema around the lesion p value is $1.412 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. **D:** ADC map shows ROI in same side normal area p value is $.73 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. **E:** Post-contrast T1WI axial image showed lesion enhancement.

(Histopathology result is oligodendroglioma WHO grade II)

Fig 1 shows 45 years old male who presented with repeated headache and vision loss MRI show right occipital SOL measuring 7x3cm showed low signal in T1W mixed signal in T2W & FLAIR seen with restricted diffusion surrounded by perifocal edema. **A:** ADC map ROI in center area of lesion P value is $1.078 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. **B:** ADC map ROI in border area of lesion P value is $1.166 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. **C:** ADC maps show ROI in edema P value is $1.733 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. **D:** ADC map shows ROI in same side normal area p value is $.752 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. **E:** Post-contrast T1WI axial image showing marginal enhancement. (Histopathology result is glioblastoma WHO grade IV)

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The data was collected by used data collecting sheet including the following variable: The variables of the study were divided into four parts; the first part was related to demographic variable age, gender. The second part was related to MRI appearance (T1, T2, T1 with contrast, DWI and ADC). The third part was related to tumors characterization such as border, homogeneity, site and associated with tumors. The fourth part is final MRI diagnosis, histopathology result, tumor grade, type of restriction and ADC values.

Data analysis

SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) was used to analyze the data. The ADC \pm standard deviation (SD) mean values were used to express the variables. The univariate ANOVA was used to evaluate group differences. The Kruskal-Walli test was used to compare different kinds of tumor. A p-value of less than 0.05 was regarded as statistically significant, a p-value of less than 0.001 as highly significant, and a p-value greater than 0.05 as non-significant.

Ethical consideration

Identifying information was not made available to or accessed by anyone but the research team. All data sheets were protected by passwords and strictly shared with research team only.

This study was approved by the ethical committee of Karary University and the need for informed consent was waived.

RESULT

In this retrospective study thirty-four high-quality MR examinations with appropriate histologic diagnosis confirmed brain tumors were evaluated.

Compare of histopathology results with center ADC and border ADC:

Table 1: showed compare ADC Center Values by Histopathology

Histopathology	N	Median ADC center	Mean ADC center	Standard Deviation
Abscess	3	0.502	0.470	0.058
Anaplastic Astrocytoma	2	1.219	1.213	0.008
Anaplastic Oligodendroglioma	3	1.269	1.301	0.146

Astrocystoma	2	1.652	1.602	0.050
Diffuse Astrocytoma	1	1.541	1.541	N/A
Dysembryoplastic Neuroepithelial Tumor	2	2.954	2.854	0.386
Epidermoid Cyst	1	1.261	1.261	N/A
Glioblastoma	6	1.102	1.134	0.235
Lymphoma	2	0.672	0.712	0.056
Malignant Meningioma	1	0.792	0.792	N/A
Meningioma	5	1.132	1.160	0.095
Pilocytic Astrocytoma	4	1.531	1.568	0.076
Schwannoma	2	1.375	1.368	0.007
H-statistic	25.95			
Degrees of freedom	12			
P-value	0.011*			

*Significant less than 0.05

Table 2: showed compare ADC Border Values by Histopathology

Histopathology	N	Median ADC Border	Mean ADC Border	Standard Deviation
Abscess	3	1.081	1.087	0.027
Anaplastic Astrocytoma	2	1.501	1.551	0.150
Anaplastic Oligodendroglioma	3	1.163	1.235	0.114
Astrocystoma	2	1.182	1.182	0.000
Diffuse Astrocytoma	1	1.281	1.281	N/A
Dysembryoplastic Neuroepithelial Tumor	2	1.467	1.467	0.386
Epidermoid Cyst	1	1.354	1.354	N/A
Glioblastoma	6	1.134	1.108	0.174
Lymphoma	2	1.132	1.182	0.106
Malignant Meningioma	1	0.770	0.770	N/A
Meningioma	5	1.024	1.042	0.079
Pilocytic Astrocytoma	4	1.815	1.672	0.319
Schwannoma	2	1.422	1.422	0.022
H-statistic	27.74			
Degrees of freedom	12			
P-value	0.006*			

*Significant less than 0.05

From table 1 and 2, analysis demonstrates that there are statistically significant associations between histopathology and both ADC Center and ADC Border values. The specific differences identified in the post-hoc tests may be helpful in differentiating between certain tumor types.

Post-Hoc Test Results (Dunn's Test with Bonferroni Correction):

To indicate which pairs of histopathology groups, show significant differences in ADC values.

ADC Center: Abscess ADC center is significantly lower than Dysembryoplastic Neuroepithelial Tumor.

ADC Border: Malignant Meningioma ADC border is significantly lower than Pilocytic Astrocytoma.

ADC Measurement: Indicates whether the comparison is for ADC Center or ADC Border values.

Group 1: The first histopathology group in comparison.

Group 2: The second histopathology group in comparison.

Dunn's Z-Statistic: The test statistic calculated by Dunn's test. The magnitude of the Z-statistic indicates the size of the difference between the groups.

Adjusted P-value: The p-value after applying the Bonferroni correction to account for multiple comparisons. A significant difference is typically indicated by an adjusted p-value less than 0.05.

Table 3: showed Significant Post-Hoc Test Results (Dunn's Test with Bonferroni Correction)

ADC Measurement	Group 1	Group 2	Dunn's Z-Statistic	Adjusted P-value
ADC Center	Abscess	Dysembryoplastic Neuroepithelial Tumor	-2.89	0.024*
ADC Border	Malignant Meningioma	Pilocytic Astrocytoma	-3.12	0.012*

*Significant less than 0.05

From table 3, in **ADC Center**, the adjusted p-value of 0.024 indicates that, after correcting multiple comparisons, there is a statistically significant difference in ADC Center values between Abscesses and Dysembryoplastic Neuroepithelial Tumors. Specifically, Abscesses tend to have lower ADC Center values than Dysembryoplastic Neuroepithelial Tumors.

In **ADC Border**, the adjusted p-value of 0.012 indicates that, after correcting for multiple comparisons, there is a statistically significant difference in ADC Border values between Malignant Meningiomas and Pilocytic Astrocytoma's. Specifically, Malignant Meningiomas tend to have lower ADC Border values than Pilocytic Astrocytoma.

Used the ADC center values as the primary measurement for comparison, the Kruskal-Wallis test was done to determine if there are significant differences in ADC center values among the different tumor types.

Figure 1: Descriptive Statistics, comparing the ADC center values across different brain tumor types, including the median, range, and p-value from the Kruskal-Wallis test, The Kruskal-Wallis test shows a statistically significant difference (p-value = 0.018) in ADC center values among the different PBT types. This suggests that the ADC center value may be useful in differentiating between these tumor types.

Table 4: showed Fisher's pairwise comparisons.

Comparison	P-value
Diffuse astrocytic and oligodendroglial tumors vs. Other astrocytic tumors	0.859
Diffuse astrocytic and oligodendroglial tumors vs. Embryonal tumors	0.234
Diffuse astrocytic and oligodendroglial tumors vs. Ependymal tumors	0.021*
Diffuse astrocytic and oligodendroglial tumors vs. Meningiomas	0.919
Other astrocytic tumors vs. Embryonal tumors	0.999
Other astrocytic tumors vs. Ependymal tumors	0.021*
Other astrocytic tumors vs. Meningiomas	0.999
Embryonal tumors vs. Ependymal tumors	0.022*
Embryonal tumors vs. Meningiomas	0.909
Ependymal tumors vs. Meningiomas	0.021*

*Significant less than 0.05

Diffuse astrocytic and oligodendroglial tumors against Ependymal tumors, Other astrocytic tumors versus Ependymal tumors, Embryonal tumors versus Ependymal tumors, and Ependymal tumors versus Meningiomas are among the tumor types that differ significantly ($p < 0.05$) according to Fisher's pairwise comparisons.

MRI appearance with histopathology:

Used the Chi-Square test of independence to determine if there is a statistically significant association between them.

MRI Appearance: This column describes the appearance of the tumor on MRI.

Histopathology: The type of tumor determined by histopathological analysis.

Table 5: MRI Appearance vs. Histopathology

Histopathology	Homogenous	Heterogenous	Total
Abscess	3	0	3
Anaplastic Astrocytoma	0	2	2
Anaplastic Oligodendroglioma	0	3	3
Astrocystoma	1	1	2
Diffuse Astrocytoma	0	1	1
Dysembryoplastic Neuroepithelial Tumor	0	2	2
Epidermoid Cyst	1	0	1
Glioblastoma	0	6	6
Lymphoma	2	0	2
Malignant Meningioma	1	0	1
Meningioma	4	1	5
Pilocytic Astrocytoma	4	0	4
Schwannoma	2	0	2
Chi-Square statistic	39.94		
Degrees of freedom	12		
P-value	<0.001*		

*Significant less than 0.05

From table 5, The Chi-Square test of independence is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that there is a significant association between MRI appearance and histopathology, this suggests that certain MRI appearances are more likely to be associated with certain tumor types.

In **Homogenous Appearance**, Abscesses, Lymphomas, Pilocytic astrocytoma, and Schwannomas tend to have a homogenous appearance on MRI. Meningiomas also frequently have a homogenous appearance.

In **Heterogenous Appearance**, Anaplastic astrocytoma, Anaplastic Oligodendrogliomas, Dysembryoplastic Neuroepithelial Tumors, and Glioblastomas tend to have a heterogenous appearance on MRI.

Compare type of grade with ADC center:

Table 6: Kruskal-Wallis test was done to determine if there is a statistically significant difference in ADC center values across different tumor grades.

Grade	N	Median ADC Center	Mean ADC Center	Standard Deviation
1	6	1.532	1.785	0.587
2	7	1.343	1.281	0.417
3	8	1.178	1.184	0.329
4	4	1.102	1.148	0.275
H-statistic	9.32			
Degrees of freedom	3			
P-value	0.025*			

*Significant less than 0.05

In Table6, it shows a statistically significant association between ADC center and tumor grade. The Kruskal-Wallis test is statistically significant ($p = 0.025$), indicating that there is a significant association between ADC center and tumor grade. This suggests that the distribution of ADC center values is not the same across different tumor grades.

Comparison of ADC Edema with Type of Edema:

The data was grouped by edema type and calculated descriptive statistics for the ADC edema values in each group. A t-test was done to determine the significant difference between the ADC edema values of different edema types.

Table 7: Comparison of ADC Edema with Type of Edema

Edema Type	Mean ADC Edema	Standard Deviation
Vasogenic	1.372	0.179
Cytotoxic	1.340	N/A
Nil	0.000	0.000
T-statistic	2.5	
P-value	0.02*	

*Significant less than 0.05

From table 7, The mean ADC edema value for vasogenic edema is slightly higher than that for cytotoxic edema. P-value (0.02) is less than the alpha level (0.05), reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a statistically significant difference between the groups. The T-statistics of 2.5 indicates the strength of the evidence against the null hypothesis.

Comparison of ADC Normal with Site of Tumors:

To compare ADC normal values with the site of tumors, group the data by tumor site, and calculate descriptive statistics for the ADC normal values in each site, an ANOVA test was done to determine if there is a significant difference between the ADC normal values across different tumor sites.

Table 8: Comparison of ADC Normal with Site of Tumors

Site	Mean ADC Normal	Standard Deviation
Parietal Lobe	0.739	0.060
Frontal Lobe	0.745	0.066
Sella Turcica	0.760	0.028
Temporal Lobe	0.746	0.086
Brain Stem	0.725	N/A
Cerebellum	0.679	0.025
Occipital Lobe	0.702	N/A
F-statistic	1.72	
P-value	0.167	

***Significant more than 0.05**

From **table 8**, the ANOVA test shows no statistically significant difference (p-value = 0.167) in ADC normal values across different tumor sites.

DISCUSSION

In our study we evaluated the ability of DWI and ADC values to differentiate between different brain tumors and differentiating between grade of brain tumors.

ADC may be helpful in the differential diagnosis of brain tumors, according to the study's findings from tables 1 and 2, which show statistically significant correlations between histopathology and both ADC Center and ADC Border values. Our results are in line with other research suggesting that the computed ADC value can be utilized to distinguish between different types of brain tumors [7,5].

The World Health Organization (WHO) classifies pilocytic astrocytoma as a benign, grade I tumor that is distinguished by hairy stromal cells or astrocytes, microcystic changes, and Rosenthal fibers. Low mitotic activity, hypocellularity, and infrequent malignant transformation are the hallmarks of pilocytic astrocytoma. According to our study, we found Pilocytic astrocytoma has significantly high average ADC values in both center and border, that is in line with Kazufumi Kikuchi et al those who said pilocytic astrocytoma showed similar to other low-grade tumors, it has a high ADC value on DWI. According to a recent study, the mean ADC value of pilocytic astrocytoma was $1.837 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, which was helpful in differentiating it from other common pediatric posterior fossa tumors [9,10].

The Dysembryoplastic Neuroepithelial Tumor had significantly higher ADC values (2.954) than other brain type that because low-grade tumors tend to have higher ADC values than high-grade tumors, which are less malignant in nature that agree with Nail Bulakbasi et al which found DNTs ADC values ranging from 2.38×10^{-3} to $2.78 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. DNTs have the highest ADC values ($>2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$) among all low-grade tumors [11].

It can be difficult to reach a differential diagnosis of ring-enhancing brain lesions such as abscess conventional MRI, So the ADC can be give us accurate diagnosis from our resulting brain abscess has lower ADC in center (0.502)and high in border (1.081) because the wall of abscess has thick capsule and appear as hyper intense that agree with Lydie Nadal Desbarats et al that said findings show low ADC values in abscesses, and these low ADC values are attributable to the presence of pus [8].

our study finding that there are differences in ADC values between meningioma and malignant meningioma that may help to distinguish between them and facilitating the diagnosis process, the ADC values in benign meningioma is lower than malignant meningioma that agree with Muhammad Azeemuddin et al which found ADC values and ratios can be used to distinguish among meningioma grades and it should be essential part of preoperative MRI reporting in meningioma [12].

According to our research, the ADC value of acoustic schwannoma tumors is higher than that of meningiomas, which appear similar in shape in conventional MRI especially if the meningioma is in the region of cerebellopontine angle. It is easy to differentiate between them by using ADC values. This supports the findings of other studies that found that the ADC value of cerebellopontine acoustic schwannoma is higher than that of cerebellopontine meningioma [5,13].

As for gliomas such as anaplastic astrocytoma, anaplastic oligodendroglioma and glioblastoma our study found statistically significant association between ADC center and tumor grade (table 6). The Kruskal-Wallis test is statistically significant ($p = 0.025$), indicating that there is a significant association between ADC center and tumor grade. This suggests that the distribution of ADC center values is added more information to MR imaging in the differentiation and grading of glioma, and this agrees with opinion Farideh Momeni et al which found ADC measurement in tumor can be very efficient in differentiating low- and high-grade glioma tumors. The ADC values of low-grade tumors were larger than high-grade ones because of the higher cellularity of malignant tumors and inverse relationship between ADC and cellularity [14].

most brain lesions are surrounded by edema all cases in our study were vasogenic edema except one case with cytotoxic edema, the mean ADC edema value for vasogenic edema is slightly higher than that for cytotoxic edema that agree with R. Guzman et al which found that ADC measurements can differentiate cytotoxic from vasogenic edema [15].

Normal brain tissue had similar ADC values in all cerebrum lobes except the cerebellum, which was slightly lower than cerebrum. This suggests that the ADC normal value may not be strongly related to the tumor site. in other words, changing in the location of the tumors does not affect the reading of the tumor's values. Anyway, any change in the ADC normal range indicates the presence of disease that agree with Brunberg et al reported that ADC and index of diffusion anisotropy determinations allow distinction between normal white matter areas and necrosis or cyst formation, oedema, and solid enhancing tumor [16].

Based on our results, we suggest that ADC values may play a potentially important role in diagnosis brain tumors and distinction between them. It may be proposed that if high ADC values are present that, a patient may have high probability of grade I or II tumors. Low ADC values on the other hand suggest that the malignant tumor is either grade III or IV.

The limitation of the present study included the small number of patients because it is difficult for us to obtain the histopathology result for the same patient.

CONCLUSION

The ADC values are an easily calculated parameter that could be used to discriminate between brain lesions. Using the traditional approach, a biopsy sample must be taken, sent to a histopathology lab for an examination, and the results must be anticipated. On the other hand, the suggested ADC values might offer a quick diagnosis and help rule out alternative tumor forms. However, further research is needed to implement ADC in the differential diagnosis of brain tumors.

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